

lemma was not eaten. Up to 50% of the top and 37% of the middle of preflowering spikelets were eaten and only 3.2% of preflowering spikelets were eaten from

the lateral side. An average 62% of preflowering spikelets were entirely eaten and 38% were partly eaten. The larvae fed on an average 24.8 spikelets/d during

various instars. During the sixth to eighth instar as many as 257 preflowering spikelets were eaten, which indicates the magnitude of grain loss. □

Controlling armyworm with synthetic pyrethroids and conventional insecticides

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For the first time, a severe outbreak of rice armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia* Boisd. occurred in IR20 nurseries in Oct 1983 at the Agricultural College Farm, Madurai. An average 400 to 420 third- and fourth-instar larvae per square meter was recorded. We evaluated three synthetic pyrethroids and four conventional insecticides for control. Insecticides were applied with a knapsack sprayer on 15-d-old nurseries in the evening. Treatments were in three replications. Living and dead larvae in a 1-m² area were counted 24 h after spraying and percent mortality was calculated (see table).

Evaluation of three synthetic pyrethroids and four conventional insecticides for control of rice armyworm larvae, Madurai, India.

Insecticide	Application rate (g ai/ha)	Larval mortality (%) ^a
FMC54800	12.5	100 a
FMC54800	25	100 a
FMC54800	50	100 a
FMC65318	15	100 a
FMC65318	30	100 a
FMC65318	45	100 a
Cypermethrin (Ripcord 10 EC)	50	100 a
Chlorpyrifos (Coroban 20 EC)	200	100 a
Endosulfan (Endocel 35 EC)	350	91.6 b
Phosalone (Zolone 35 EC)	350	84.9 c
Heptachlor 20 EC	500	84.1 c
Check		

^a Calculated 24h after insecticide treatment. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

FMC54800, FMC65318, cypermethrin, and chlorpyrifos were the most effective chemicals. □

Effect of insecticide application on rice growth

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Brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is the most serious rice pest in many Asian countries. We studied plant growth and biochemical changes in rice plants after foliar insecticide application.

Two 10-day-old TN1 seedlings were transplanted in 12-cm clay pots and sprayed with insecticides 20, 30, and 40 d after planting under pest-free conditions. There were 12 treatments (see table) and 3 replications. Control plants were sprayed with water. Fifteen days after the last spraying, the number of tillers and leaves and plant height in each treatment were recorded. Nutrient changes caused by insecticide application were determined by sampling 20 cm of leaf sheath and stem above the soil. Samples were dried and analyzed for total N, P, K, Ca, and Mg.

Foliar application of fenthion, methyl

Plant hosts of rice caseworm

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Twelve rice field weeds were compared to

Effect of foliar application of insecticide on TN1 plant growth, Aduthurai, India.^a

Treatment ^b	Mean numbers		Plant ht (cm)
	Tillers	Leaves	
Fenthion	8.0 a	29.0 a	72.7 a
Methyl parathion	10.0 a	30.7 a	75.7 a
Quinalphos	7.7 b	26.3 b	75.0 a
Phosphamidon	7.3 bc	25.7 bc	75.0 a
Carbosulfan	7.3 bc	24.7 c	73.7 a
BPMC	7.0 c	23.7 cd	72.3 a
Methamidophos	7.0 c	22.3 d	70.3 a
Fenvalerate	7.7 b	25.7 b	73.3 a
Permethrin	9.0 a	24.7 c	71.7 a
Cypermethrin	8.0 b	28.3 ab	74.7 a
Deltamethrin	9.0 a	29.0 a	76.0 a
Untreated check	6.7 c	20.3 b	72.3 a

^aData are means of three replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bThe first seven are insecticides applied at 0.04%. The next four are pyrethroids applied at 0.002%.

parathion, permethrin, and deltamethrin increased tillering (see table), as did application of quinalphos, fenvalerate, cypermethrin, phosphamidon, and carbosulfan. BPMC and methamidophos did not affect tillering. Plant height was not affected by insecticide application; neither was nutrient content. Results suggest that lush growth after insecticide application might attract immigrating BPH □

rice as hosts of rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (see table). Rice caseworm eggs from a greenhouse colony were placed in cages around potted vegetative-stage plants immersed in water. Developing larvae were forced to feed on one plant species in this no-choice trial.

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